

Biomimetic pHEMA hydrogels as an alternative cartilage-like model material for biotribological evaluations

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ABSTRACT

Poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) has been widely explored as a model material for articular cartilage (AC) in biotribological evaluations. However, PVA hydrogels prepared by freeze-thawing or cast-drying methods have limitations in precisely controlling their elasticity parameters and may require reinforcement to enhance their mechanical performance and change their transparency, required in some tribological measurement setups using fluorescence methods. To overcome these issues, poly(hydroxyethyl methacrylate) (pHEMA) hydrogels have been introduced as alternatives. In our study, pHEMA hydrogels synthesised using free-radical polymerisation with blue light under two different atmospheres (N_2 and air) were compared with natural samples of articular bovine cartilage. Its optical, mechanical, swelling and tribological properties demonstrate the superior properties of pHEMA, which may result in the replacement of the currently used PVA-based model in future studies. Synthesis under a nitrogen atmosphere (*pHEMA N_2*) resulted in the formation of smooth-surfaced hydrogels, whereas synthesis under a laboratory atmosphere (*pHEMA air*) resulted in the formation of corrugated-surfaced hydrogels, which were more similar to the AC surface. The swelling of both hydrogels and AC followed first-order kinetics. Pin-on-plate biotribology measurements showed that the coefficient of friction (COF) of the corrugated-surface hydrogels resembled that of AC. In terms of permeability, *pHEMA air* is a faithful model of healthy human cartilage, whereas *pHEMA N_2* can be a model of cartilage with incipient osteoarthritis. Our results showed that pHEMA-based hydrogels are suitable biotribological articular cartilage models for a better understanding of the biological function of articular cartilage. Knowledge brings new insights into the cartilage complex mechanisms and might be imitated in both biomedical as well as engineering applications.

KEYWORDS: pHEMA hydrogels, crosslinking, biotribology, biomechanics, articular cartilage, coefficient of friction

INTRODUCTION

Human articular cartilage (AC) has a vital function in absorbing joint pressure during movement and minimising friction between bones[1]. Articular cartilage is a complex form of connective tissue primarily composed of hyaline cartilage, which plays a vital role in bearing weight, absorbing shock, and facilitating lubrication in joints throughout the body to minimise friction[2]. AC is a specialised type of hyaline cartilage, the most common cartilage in the human body, usually measuring 2–4 mm in thickness[3]. It consists of approximately 60–80% water, 15–22% collagen, 5–10% chondrocytes, 4–7% proteoglycans, minerals (less than 4%), and matrix proteins (less than 1%)[4,5], forming a complex composition that forms a vascular-free structure without nerves or lymphatics[6]. AC is defined as a porous, viscoelastic substance comprising three main phases: a solid extracellular matrix (ECM) phase, a fluid phase containing water (interstitial fluid), and an ion phase (composed of dissolved electrolytes with both negative and positive charges, less than 1%). These phases allow the tissue to withstand compressive forces[2,7]. As it is exposed to different types of external forces, such as compression, tension, shear, and friction, it exhibits impressive strength (ranging from 9 to 40 MPa) and toughness (with a fracture energy of 1,000 to 15,000 J·m⁻²), and shows a significant strain at failure (ranging from 60 to 120 %)[8–10]. AC is an anisotropic material with four specific zones: the superficial (or tangential) zone (representing 10–20% of the AC thickness), middle (or transitional) zone (accounting for 40–60 % of the total cartilage volume), deep (or radial) zone (constituting approximately 30 % of the AC volume), and calcified zone[11].

Various structural elements within cartilage, such as collagen fibres, proteoglycans, and water content, dictate its biophysical characteristics and ability to endure mechanical stresses. The integrity of the cartilage is influenced by mechanical loading, and research has highlighted the necessity of replicating the biomechanical environment of chondrocytes for effective tissue engineering and repair[12]. Additionally, the sluggish metabolic rate of cartilage, a consequence of its lack of blood supply, hampers its regenerative capacity, thus contributing to the onset of chronic conditions such as osteoarthritis (OA)[13]. Tissue engineering offers a promising avenue for investigating the mechanisms of cartilage regeneration by leveraging cells and hydrogels to promote chondrogenic differentiation in laboratory settings, thereby enhancing their therapeutic potential for in vivo applications[1,14,15].

To understand the tribology of cartilage and lubrication mechanisms for future implications and possible applications of artificial cartilage in clinical practice, several materials have been investigated as model materials for tribological measurements and research. Hydrogels based on polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and its copolymers have garnered interest in various scientific investigations[16]. The use of PVA hydrogels presents several advantages, such as favourable biocompatibility, reduced friction, and the capacity to simulate the behaviour of natural tissues[17–19]. Typically, the elasticity parameters of PVA hydrogels produced through conventional freeze-thaw (FT) or cast-drying (CD) techniques cannot be precisely regulated because they are influenced mainly by two factors: molecular weight and the number of freezing cycles[20,21]. Nevertheless, the primary drawback is the subpar mechanical characteristics of these hydrogels, which impede their potential to effectively substitute natural cartilage[22–24]. To counter this constraint, researchers have developed diverse methodologies to improve the mechanical properties of PVA hydrogels, including the integration of reinforcing fibres, such as poly(p-phenylene-2,6-benzobisoxazole) (PBO) nanofibres[25], phosphate glass fibres (PGF), poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG), ramie fibres[26], cellulose[27], poly(ethylene) (PE)[28,29], and biodegradable glass fibres[30]. Numerous studies have introduced bionic and hybrid hydrogels by combining PVA with polymers, such as poly(acrylamide) (PAM)[31], poly(acrylic acid) (PAA)[32], sodium phytate (PANA)[33], gum Karaya[34,35], and poly(ethylene glycol)/glycerol[36,37] to increase their efficacy and drug conveyance capacities[38,39]. In essence, PVA-based hydrogels and their blends continue to advance, providing reduced friction, elevated mechanical robustness, and improved drug delivery capabilities, notwithstanding the pivotal impact of preparation methodologies and the need for further optimisation which remain notable challenges[40].

Frictional measurements in pin-on-plate[41,42] or pin-on-disc[42] configurations are commonly used to study the lubrication mechanism of AC. These methods assess the evolution of the coefficient of friction (COF) between two AC samples[1], sometimes replaced by a glass[43] or PVA hydrogel[44]. However, these studies do not provide sufficient insight into the underlying mechanisms necessary to understand the lubrication regimes of AC. Our research group has developed a methodology[45] that combines frictional measurements in a pin-on-plate configuration with simultaneous in situ observation of the contact area by fluorescence microscopy. This method enables the direct observation of fluorescently labelled proteins and HA

clusters in the AC contact and the formation of a boundary lubricating layer on the AC surface. This methodology requires one of the contact surfaces to be transparent. The optical glass used thus far is not an ideal substitute in terms of mechanical properties, porosity, and so on. One of the most widely accepted theories of AC lubrication - hydration lubrication[46] assumes the interaction between phospholipids in SF and HA attached to the AC surface. This interaction is crucial for exposing the positively charged phospholipid heads and for the diffusion-driven exchange of water molecules in their hydration shells, leading to the extremely low COF values, around 0.010, reported for AC[47]. However, HA or phospholipids cannot bind to inert glass, making cartilage-on-glass an inadequate substitute for analysing AC hydration lubrication mechanisms.

Our study aims to develop a material that can be used as a substitute for the currently used PVA hydrogel or optical glass in tribological testing with a pin-on-plate tribometer and in our setup using fluorescence microscopy. **For the material to be suitable for superlubricity measurements, in combination with observations using fluorescence microscopy, it must be transparent with well-defined mechanical, chemical, and swelling properties that are ideally similar to those of AC.**

The poly(hydroxyethyl methacrylate) (pHEMA)-based hydrogels used in our study are ideal candidates for replacing AC and the currently prevailing model PVA hydrogels, mainly because of their low friction coefficients and mechanical properties, which resemble those of the natural cartilage[48]. In general, pHEMA hydrogels can be produced by radical polymerisation with adjustable swelling and mechanical properties, providing good reproducibility and reduced cost compared to natural hydrogels[49]. Nevertheless, pHEMA materials may also require reinforcement for improved mechanical performance, similar to that of PVA hydrogels reinforced with PBO nanofibers [50].

However, enhancements in pore size, stability, and rigidity are essential for enhancing cell conductivity[51]. Additionally, pHEMA can be altered to facilitate drug delivery to the deep zones of cartilage, thus serving as an efficient carrier for treating osteoarthritis [51,52].

The primary benefit of pHEMA-based hydrogels is their ability to customise their mechanical properties by adjusting a few key parameters, such as the crosslinking mechanism or monomer concentration. This allows for the imposition of the desired mechanical properties, including

elasticity, rigidity, stability, and appearance[53]. With the ability to make materials either transparent or translucent, pHEMA-based hydrogels offer a versatile solution for a wide range of tribological applications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

To prepare **pHEMA hydrogels**, 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany), 2,2-dimethoxy-2-phenylacetophenone (DMPA) from Acros Organics (Thermo Fisher Scientific, UK), and ethylene glycol dimethacrylate (EGDMA) from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany). The MilliQ water Type 1 (ISO 3696) was prepared using a Millipore purification system (Milli-Q Academic, France).

Physiological solution (PS) was purchased from B. Braun (Germany), and hyaluronic acid HySilk (HA) with a molecular weight of 820–1020 kDa for the preparation of synovial fluid was purchased from Contipro a.s. (Czech Republic). L- α -phosphatidylcholine was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA). Potassium chloride, sodium chloride, potassium dihydrogen phosphate, and disodium hydrogen phosphate dodecahydrate were purchased from LachNer (Czech Republic) for the preparation of the phosphate buffer (PBS). Bovine serum albumin and γ -globulin were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA). A high-intensity UV lamp (T8, 18 W, 60 cm) with a wavelength of 365 nm, was purchased from Eurolite (Germany).

Methods

Synthesis of HEMA hydrogel samples

Transparent pHEMA hydrogels were prepared by free-radical polymerisation of monomer HEMA, crosslinker EGDMA, photoinitiator DMPA, and MilliQ water under an inert (nitrogen) atmosphere or in air at laboratory temperature. The synthesis of water-based pHEMA hydrogels was inspired by our previous work[54], in which monomer HEMA was added at 60% w/w, DMPA was adjusted to 0.25–0.5% w/w and crosslinker 0.25–1% w/w. First, the photoinitiator, monomer, water and the crosslinker were mixed. The liquid mixture was transferred to a mould with a fixed volume attached to tribological glass at the bottom, where polymerisation occurred. The solution was irradiated with a 365 nm, 15 W UV lamp (emission in the visible region) at a fixed distance of 10 cm from the centre of the samples, with an irradiation period of less than 20 min. The synthesis was performed either under a nitrogen atmosphere in a plastic container with a closed lid under

constant nitrogen flow (*pHEMA N2*) or under laboratory atmosphere, 23 °C, humidity 28% (*pHEMA air*).

Preparation of cartilage samples

Cartilage samples were obtained from bovine femoral heads within 24 h of slaughter in a local butcher shop. The fresh joints were stored in a refrigerator at 4 °C prior to sample extraction. For the static swelling tests, cartilage specimens were obtained from the centre of the femoral head using a precise cutting tool (standardised punch, diameter 4 mm)[55] to create uniform cartilage disks without subchondral bone. For tribological measurements, the femoral head was cut with an oscillating saw to harvest plate samples (approximately 45 × 20 mm in size). Cartilage pins with a diameter of approximately 9.7 mm in diameter were pressed from some of these plates using a custom-designed punch. Depending on the condition and size of the femoral head, a maximum of one cartilage plate or two pin samples were obtained from each femoral head. The cartilage plates and pins were removed, along with the subchondral bone, to clamp the tribometer. The samples were stored in a phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) at -22 °C before the experiments to prevent cartilage degradation.

Tensile testing

To obtain reference values for the tensile stress (σ_t), tensile strength (ε_0), and Young's modulus (E_t) of the samples, a series of uniaxial tensile tests following the ISO 527 standard were conducted using a Zwick Roell Z010 material testing machine. A 500 N load cell was used to test the pHEMA hydrogel samples in a dogbone 5A shape. The tests were performed at a preload speed of 5 mm·min⁻¹ to reach a preload force of 1 N, followed by a load speed of 2 mm·min⁻¹ in the linear region of tensile testing, and finally, 20 mm·min⁻¹ to achieve a 50% decrease in the maximal force (F_{max}). Young's modulus (E_t) was calculated from the slope of the linear-elastic region of the stress-strain curve using Formula (1):

$$E_t = \frac{\sigma_1}{\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_1}, \quad (1)$$

where ε_1 and ε_2 are values of stress (MPa) corresponding to relative deformations between 0.0005–0.0025 (-).

The stress was calculated using Eq. (2):

$$\sigma_i = \frac{F_i}{A}, \quad (2)$$

where F_i is the applied force at the given time point and A is a cross-section area of the “neck” part of the dogbone sample.

The deformation was calculated using Equation (3):

$$\varepsilon_i = \frac{L_i - L_0}{L_0}, \quad (3)$$

where L_i is the actual sample elongation (mm) and L_0 is the initial length of the measured part of the sample (mm).

According to the ISO 527 standard, the initial length L_0 was set to 50 mm. The experiments were conducted in a series of $n=5$ tests at laboratory temperature (23 °C).

Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR)

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy was used to characterise the chemical composition of the dried pHEMA sample surface. ATR-FTIR Hyperion 3000/Vertex70v (Bruker, USA) with a germanium ATR crystal was used, and the measurements were performed under evacuated conditions. Spectra in the wavenumber range of 4,000–650 cm^{-1} were obtained by averaging 100 scans per sample with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . The spectra were normalised using min-max normalisation (OPUS software, Bruker, USA).

Static Swelling Test

PHEMA hydrogels and cartilage samples in the form of 4 mm discs were left to dry overnight in a laboratory oven (Ecocell 111, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Czech Republic) at a temperature of 50 °C until they reached a constant weight. The thickness average thickness of pHEMA hydrogels was 2.0 ± 0.2 mm, and the thickness of the cartilage samples was 2.2 ± 0.2 mm. A solution of synovial fluid comprising 0.5% w/v HA in Milli-Q water was utilised, given the extended testing period during which γ -globulin and bovine serum albumin may deteriorate. The samples were then immersed in excess physiological water or synovial fluid, and incubated at 37 °C. Subsequently, the samples were wiped with a lint-free cloth, and the amount of water absorbed was determined using gravimetric analysis at various time intervals, namely, 30, 60, and 90 min, as well as at 2, 5, 24, and 48 h. The experiments were performed in a series of $n=5$ tests, and the swelling of the hydrogels was calculated using Eq. (4):

$$\text{Swelling ratio (\%)} = \frac{W_1 - W_0}{W_0} \cdot 100, \quad (4)$$

where W_0 is the initial weight of the dried sample and W_1 is the weight of the swollen sample at the defined time interval.

A first-order swelling model was used to fit the experimental data and to examine the swelling control process. Eq. (5) was used to calculate first-order kinetics[56,57].

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = k_1 \cdot (S_{max} - S), \quad (5)$$

where k_1 is the rate constant for first-order swelling kinetics, S is the degree of swelling at a specific time point, and S_{max} is the degree of swelling at equilibrium.

The first-order (k_1) swelling constant and S_{max} were calculated by fitting the experimental data to the model in Excel using the function 'Solver' with the parameters set to be larger than or equal to zero.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The surface morphologies of dried PHEMA hydrogel and cartilage samples were examined. The samples were dried overnight in a laboratory oven Ecocell 111 at 50 °C until a constant weight was obtained. The surfaces of the HEMA and cartilage samples were coated with a 15 nm-thick gold layer using a Leica EM ACE600 coater (Leica, Germany). Imaging was performed using a MIRA3-XMU microscope (Tescan, Czech Republic) at suitable magnifications and a working distance at a high voltage of 5 kV. Images were processed using ImageJ 2 software (National Institutes of Health, USA).

Tribology

To determine the frictional properties of pHEMA hydrogels, reciprocating sliding tests were conducted using a universal tribometer (UMT Tribolab, Bruker, USA). Sliding tests employed a pin-on-plate configuration shown in **Figure 1** to examine the coefficient of friction (COF) as a function of time[58]. The contact pair consists of a stationary plate composed of a pHEMA hydrogel and a moving cartilage pin. For reference, a sliding test was performed with a cartilage pin sliding against a plate. During the test, the cartilage pin was subjected to a constant load of 5

N and a reciprocating sliding motion at a speed of $10 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ with a stroke length of 12 mm. Each test lasted for 30 min. The contact pair was fully flooded with artificial synovial fluid and the lubricant with the plate sample was heated to $37 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [59]. The experiments were performed in $n=5$ tests per sample type.

Figure 1. Scheme of a pin-on-plate setup for the determination of COF of the pHEMA hydrogels against a cartilage pin.

For tribological testing, artificial synovial fluid was prepared according to the method described by Galandaková et al. (2017)[60]. Briefly, $2.5 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$ HA, $0.15 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$ L- α -phosphatidylcholine, $20 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$ bovine serum albumin, and, $3.6 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$ γ -globulin were added to a PBS solution (2.68 mM potassium chloride, 136.89 mM sodium chloride, 0.56 mM potassium dihydrogen phosphate, 23.59 mM disodium hydrogen phosphate dodecahydrate) and mixed until dissolved.

Estimation of permeability by stress relaxation tests

The permeability of pHEMA was estimated through stress-relaxation tests conducted using an Autograph AGS-X testing machine (Shimadzu, Japan) equipped with a 100 N capacity SM-100n-168 load cell. mm (for pHEMA specimens, with dimensions of $20 \times 10 \text{ mm}$ and thicknesses of 2.50 mm (for pHEMA air, $n=3$) and 2.66 mm (for pHEMA N2, $n=3$), were subjected to compression under a 30 mm diameter aluminium cylinder. The applied strain was maintained at 15% and the relaxation time was set to $21,600 \text{ s}$. Throughout the compression tests, the samples were submerged in a pure water bath to replicate physiological conditions. The permeability was estimated using the method described by Yamaguchi et al. (2018)[61] based on the relaxation function $E(t)$ in Eq. (6).

$$E(t) = E_{\infty} + E_1 \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_1}} + E_2 \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_2}}, \quad (6)$$

Where E_∞ represents the relaxed modulus, E_1 and τ_1 are the intensity and characteristic time of the **shorter** relaxation mode, and E_2 and τ_2 correspond to the intensity and characteristic time of the **longer** relaxation mode.

The parameters were determined using the least-squares method, with the maximum load time designated as $t = 0$. The shear storage modulus G was calculated using Eq. (7).

$$G = \frac{\sigma_z(t = 0)}{3\varepsilon_z} = \frac{E_\infty + E_1 + E_2}{3}, \quad (7)$$

where ε_z is applied strain, and σ_z represents the initial stress, calculated using Eq. (8).

$$\sigma_z(t = 0) = E_\infty \varepsilon_z = \frac{3 \cdot G \cdot K}{K + \frac{G}{3}} \cdot \varepsilon_z \quad (8)$$

where E_∞ is the relaxed modulus, ε_z is applied strain, G is the shear storage modulus, K is the osmotic modulus.

The osmotic modulus K was calculated using Eq. (9).

$$K = \frac{G \cdot E_\infty}{9 \cdot G - 3 \cdot E_\infty}, \quad (9)$$

where G is the shear storage modulus and E_∞ is the relaxed modulus.

The relationship between the relaxation time τ_2 and diffusion coefficient (DC) is expressed as in Eq.(10).

$$\tau_2 = \frac{1}{DC} \cdot \frac{1}{\pi^2 \left(\frac{1}{L^2 + W^2} \right)}, \quad (10)$$

where L and W are the length and width of the sample, respectively.

The values were calculated by fitting the experimental data to the model in Excel using the function ‘Solver’. Finally, the coefficient of permeability, k , was calculated using Eq. (11).

$$k = \frac{DC}{(1 - \varphi) \cdot \left(K + \frac{4}{3 \cdot G} \right)}, \quad (10)$$

where φ is the polymer volume fraction, K is the osmotic modulus, and G is the shear storage modulus.

Statistical analysis

Data are presented as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD) unless otherwise specified. The unpaired Student's t-test was used to compare two groups, whereas one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test was used to analyse more than two groups. The level of statistical significance was set at $P < 0.05$. The data were assessed using the OriginPro 2020b software (OriginLab Corporation, USA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Appearance and Morphology

Polymerisation parameters, including solvents, additives, and conditions, significantly affect the morphological characteristics of pHEMA hydrogels, indirectly leading to differences in the mechanical strength or swelling capacity, which are critical factors in their suitability for biomedical applications.

First, the concentrations of the HEMA monomer and DMPA initiator were optimised to ensure the good optical properties of the hydrogels. As shown in

Figure 2, the pHEMA hydrogels had a homogenous structure, which contributed to their good transparency[62] at the selected concentrations of HEMA and DMPA. Based on stiffness and transparency perceived through visual observation, pHEMA hydrogels with 60% w/w HEMA monomer, 0.5% w/w DMPA initiator, and 1.0% w/w EGDMA crosslinker content were used in this study.

Figure 2. Hydrogels based on different HEMA monomer concentrations (% w/w) and initiator DMPA concentrations (% w/w).

Furthermore, we investigated the influence of environmental conditions on the surface morphology of pHEMA hydrogels. Upon casual inspection, morphological disparities were observed between the samples based on the selected formulation prepared in a laboratory setting (*pHEMA air*) and those prepared under a nitrogen atmosphere (*pHEMA N2*). The morphologies of the samples are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Images of the dried samples: (A) *pHEMA N2*, (B) *pHEMA air*, and (C) bovine cartilage of the original size (first row) and SEM of their according surfaces with 200 and 10 μm scale bars (second and third row, respectively).

Observing the samples with SEM, the *pHEMA air* and cartilage samples exhibited a corrugated surface, whereas the *pHEMA N2* samples had smooth surfaces, as observed by Podestà et al. (2005)[63]. Similar wrinkling patterns were generated on pHEMA by Yun et al. (2019)[64] under laboratory conditions. Our results show that wrinkling can be controlled not only by the initiator concentration and layer thickness in the study by Yun et al. but also by changes in atmospheric conditions.

Examination of the composition of bovine AC revealed that the surface displayed a more pronounced level of wrinkling than both *pHEMA air* and *pHEMA N2*. However, the AC and *pHEMA* hydrogels exhibit disparate structural characteristics. As shown in Figure 3 (C), the top layer of the AC is transparent and rigid, whereas the deeper zones of the cartilage were spongy and porous. These disparities present avenues for future research to replicate cartilage layers in *pHEMA* hydrogels more accurately. Despite this, *pHEMA N2* exhibited properties considerably closer to those of natural AC than those of *pHEMA air*.

Structural Characterisation

Figure 4A shows the ATR-FTIR spectra of the *pHEMA* precursor, HEMA monomer, DMPA photoinitiator, and EGDMA crosslinker. The monomer **HEMA** has characteristic transmission wavenumbers at 1637 and 816 cm^{-1} , corresponding to —C=C— , and a broad —OH peak in the range between 3200–3700 cm^{-1} . The spectra of the cross-linker **EGDMA** exhibited the characteristic stretching vibrations of —C=C— at 1640 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the presence of alkenes. The —C=C— band at 1640 cm^{-1} observed in the crosslinker (EGDMA) completely disappeared in the spectra of the crosslinked networks of the *pHEMA* hydrogels, as shown in Figure 4B. This disappearance indicates the consumption of double bonds during the crosslinking. In the spectrum of pure **DMPA**, the most intense bands were attributed to the vibrations of the methyl groups in the wide range of 2800–3000 cm^{-1} , aromatic rings at 1577–1595 and 1455–1490 cm^{-1} , carbonyl groups at 1690 cm^{-1} , and C—O bonds at 1000–1160 cm^{-1} , correlating with the results of Kaczmarek et al. (2010)[65].

The chemical composition of the *pHEMA* hydrogel surface was evaluated in the dry state. The spectra of the *pHEMA* hydrogels prepared in both laboratory and nitrogen atmospheres are shown in Figure 5. In both spectra, the broad bands within the range of 3600–3150 cm^{-1} are attributed to the stretching vibrations of the hydroxyl groups (O—H) [66,67]. In the region of 1760–1650 cm^{-1} , the bands at 1723 cm^{-1} are attributed to the stretching vibrations of the carbonyl groups (C=O)[68,69]. Additionally, in the region 1404–1379 cm^{-1} , the bands correspond to the bending vibrations of methylene groups ($\text{—CH}_2\text{—}$), and the bands in the region 1321–1032 cm^{-1} are attributed to the stretching vibrations of the C—O—C groups. The *pHEMA* hydrogel prepared in the laboratory atmosphere showed (at 1690 cm^{-1}) the photoinitiator DMPA photolysis residues, such as methylbenzoate, 1,2-Diphenylethane-1,2-dione or 2,3-Diphenylbutane-2,3-diol[70,71], indicating the origin of the wrinkling patterns.

Figure 4. (A) Transmission ATR-FTIR spectra of the hydrogel precursors showing the spectra of the HEMA monomer, EDGMA crosslinker, and DMPA initiator; (B) Enlarged profile of the marked region in (A). Marked in red are the alkene —C=C— peaks in HEMA and EDGMA disappeared during the formation of the crosslinked pHEMA network.

Figure 5. (A) Transmission ATR-FTIR spectra of the pHEMA hydrogels prepared in different atmospheres; hydrogels prepared under nitrogen atmosphere in *red*; and in standard laboratory atmosphere in *blue*. (B) Enlarged profile of the marked region in (A) showing the presence of photoinitiator residues in the spectra of *pHEMA air*.

Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties closely related to the flexibility of the pHEMA hydrogels were investigated immediately after their synthesis in the wet state using tensile tests. The engineering tensile stress-strain curves of *pHEMA air* and *pHEMA N2* are plotted in Figure 6A, and a comparison of Young's moduli and tensile elongation of the two hydrogels is shown in Figure 6B. The Young's moduli were calculated from the linear-elastic region of the stress-strain curves, showing the E_t 0.93 ± 0.07 MPa and the tensile elongation of $100.71 \pm 8.53\%$ for the *pHEMA air* and 0.82 ± 0.05 MPa and $42.03 \pm 5.06\%$ for the *pHEMA N2*, respectively.

Figure 6. (A) Tensile curves of pHEMA hydrogels and (B) Young's modulus (*blue*) and tensile elongation (*pink*) of pHEMA hydrogels.

Even though the results are comparable to the results of Alqahtani S., et al. (2023)[72] and Zhu J., et al. (2013)[73], most of the studies on the mechanical properties of pHEMA hydrogels are conducted in a wet or swollen state or in the form of thin films. In such studies, the Young's modulus of 16.8 MPa has been achieved by Bose R., et al. (2010)[74] or between 0.25–59.4 MPa reported by Boazak E., et al. (2019)[75] on pHEMA hydrogels containing EGDMA and vinyl methacrylate. Although the toughness of EGDMA-crosslinked hydrogels has been reported by Moghadam et al. (2015)[76], the tensile strength of dry HEMA-EGDMA-based materials has not

yet been reported. However, the mechanical properties depend not only on the moisture content in the hydrogels but also on the testing conditions, including the parameters of preload and load speed.

Comparing the data to the mechanical properties of healthy AC, Petitjean et al. (2023)[77] concluded that the elastic modulus ranged from 250 kPa to 3 MPa in compression, whereas Akizuki et al. (1986)[78] reported a tensile modulus of AC between 1 and 15 MPa. Overall, the tensile strength of the prepared *pHEMA air* had properties which might be comparable to those of the AC used in the tribology experiments.

Static swelling behaviour

The swelling behaviours of two types of pHEMA hydrogels, *pHEMA N2* with a smooth surface and *pHEMA air* with a corrugated surface were investigated using two different fluids: commercial physiological solution (PS) and synovial fluid (SF). These findings were compared with the swelling behaviour of bovine AC in the same media. The data were fitted to first-order kinetic equations and the first-order swelling constant k_1 with the degree of swelling at equilibrium S_{max} was calculated, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Calculated first-order rate constant k_1 , the correlation coefficient R^2 , and the predicted degree of swelling at equilibrium S_{max} of the pHEMA hydrogels and AC samples in physiological water and synovial fluid.

	Physiological water			Synovial fluid		
	<i>pHEMA N2</i>	<i>pHEMA air</i>	<i>AC</i>	<i>pHEMA N2</i>	<i>pHEMA air</i>	<i>AC</i>
k_1 (h ⁻¹)	1.58±0.40	1.38±0.17	20.90±13.49	1.29±0.54	1.04±0.29	27.57±4.02
R^2 (-)	0.99±0.01	0.98±0.01	0.97±0.03	0.98±0.01	0.97±0.02	0.93±0.07
S_{max} (%)	49.97±3.27	65.49±8.51	164.37±37.86	53.61±2.40	60.32±9.45	219.08±54.01

The calculated swelling ratios of the pHEMA and AC samples, fitted with the first-order kinetic model, are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Swelling ratios of pHEMA hydrogels prepared under nitrogen and laboratory atmospheres compared with cartilage samples in physiological water (*left*) and synovial fluid (*right*). The time points were fitted using a first-order swelling kinetic model.

The swelling of the **AC samples** was significantly greater than that of both types of pHEMA hydrogels, both in PS and SF. The initial increase in fluid content was evident during the 30-minute swelling period and the calculated k_t , which in the case of PS was $20.90 \pm 13.49 \text{ h}^{-1}$ whereas in the case of SF reached $27.57 \pm 4.02 \text{ h}^{-1}$, both rate constants indicating a very fast initial swelling of the AC samples. At this point, the swelling ratio in PS reached $140.6 \pm 39.6\%$, whereas that in SF reached $222.8 \pm 43.3\%$. The AC samples were initially completely dried and the cartilage matrix was rehydrated from its entire volume. The overall swelling capacity gradually decreased over time, until the equilibrium was reached at $202.4 \pm 49.3\%$ in the case of SF (predicted S_{max} 219.08 ± 54.01), compared to the $125.5 \pm 35.8\%$ of the AC samples submerged in PS (predicted S_{max} 164.37 ± 37.86), indicating a fluid-specific[79] response of the AC to the SF containing hyaluronic acid, present in the human synovial fluid.

Owing to the substantial difference in osmotic pressure between the AC matrix and the surrounding fluid, the AC matrix rapidly absorbed the fluid and swelled. Moreover, a direct interaction between the collagen type II fibrils of the cartilage and the SF containing hyaluronic acid[80] has affected the swelling, increasing the swelling capacity of the cartilage[81]. Over time, the disparity in osmotic pressure decreased, the rate of fluid uptake diminished until equilibrium was reached, and net fluid movement into the cartilage stabilised. The osmotic properties of the

surrounding fluid also explain why swelling is more pronounced in SF than in PS. The PS, which is a relatively ‘simple’ saline solution (0.9% NaCl) containing mainly sodium and chloride ions with an osmotic pressure similar to that of extracellular fluid, exhibited a lower swelling capacity than SF. [80][81] This is further supported by the greater osmotic pressure difference between the fluid and the AC matrix in SF[82]. This finding supports the notion that natural cartilage has a superior capacity to absorb fluids, which are essential for proper joint function. Moreover, enhanced swelling in synovial fluid highlights the adaptability of bovine cartilage to the joint environment, where synovial fluid is naturally present[83]. A paired comparison of the three materials is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Paired comparison between swelling ratios (%) of the observed *pHEMA* hydrogels and AC samples in PS (*left*) and SF (*right*) at the end of the test. The results are presented as the mean \pm standard deviation of the mean, $n=5$ /group; p -values resulting from Tukey’s test with statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) are marked *, p -values reaching statistical significance ($p < 0.01$) are marked **, and p -values reaching significance ($p < 0.001$) are marked ***.

The osmotic effect of the swelling fluid was much less pronounced with the **pHEMA hydrogels** (mostly because of the regular structure of the hydrogel network compared with the collagen-based matrix of the cartilage). Looking at the swelling of the smooth *pHEMA N2*, the maximal swelling in the PS was $52.3 \pm 4.1\%$, with a swelling rate of $1.58 \pm 0.40 \text{ h}^{-1}$, while in the SF, the swelling exhibited $53.5 \pm 2.5\%$ with the swelling rate of $1.29 \pm 0.54 \text{ h}^{-1}$, showing that the swelling rate and the maximal swelling capacity were similar in both media. Nevertheless, the results are comparable to those of swelling studies performed on similar *pHEMA* structures in a disodium phosphate buffer[84]. On the other hand, the corrugated *pHEMA air* exhibited maximal swelling in PS

63.5±8.5% with a rate of 1.38±0.17 h⁻¹, while the hydrogels swelled up to 60.6±9.0% with a rate of 1.04±0.29 h⁻¹ in the SF.

These results are comparable to our previous work on the pHEMA hydrogels with 60% w/w HEMA content (Krajňák, et al., 2022)[54], where the maximum swelling ratio was approximately 50% in MilliQ water. In regard to the salt present in the PS, the pHEMA-based hydrogels show lower swelling with increasing content of the salt, as discussed by Baker et al. (1995)[85] and Pan S. et al. (2020)[86]. Additionally, Refojo et al. (1967)[87] and Kim et al. (2004)[88] showed that the solubility of hydrophobic pHEMA segments is decreased in the presence of electrolytes, strengthening the hydrophobic bonds and domains in the polymer.

In summary, despite the variation in the swelling of the cartilage and pHEMA hydrogels in the synovial fluid used in our tribological trials, the swelling kinetics of pHEMA hydrogels were remarkably consistent. A crucial consideration is that the swelling of *pHEMA air* is slightly greater than that of *pHEMA N2* in the synovial fluid, implying that employing *pHEMA air* with a higher SF absorption capacity (compared to *pHEMA N2*) would be advantageous for future experiments, as we endeavoured to achieve swelling behaviour similar to that of AC.

Tribology

The frictional behaviour of *pHEMA N2* and *pHEMA air* in contact with AC lubricated with artificial SF was investigated and the results are shown in **Figure 9**. To assess the ability of the pHEMA hydrogels to mimic AC behaviour, the results were compared with measurements of cartilage-on-cartilage contact under the same conditions. The results of all measurements are plotted in Figure 8. AC reported the lowest initial COF value of 0.0159±0.0006, with only a slight increase during the 30-minute frictional test. At the end of the measurements, the cartilage-on-cartilage contact exhibited a COF value of 0.0173±0.0006. Comparatively similar results were obtained for *pHEMA air* with a corrugated surface. The initial COF in the contact, 0.0299 ± 0.0030, as in the case of AC, increased only slightly to 0.0320±0.0037. In contrast, *pHEMA N2* with a smooth surface showed significantly different results. The initial COF value (0.0917±0.0193) was many times higher than those of the other two materials and increased rapidly during the test. The final COF value of 0.3750±0.237 was an order of magnitude higher than those of AC and *pHEMA air*.

Figure 9. Coefficient of friction of pHEMA hydrogels prepared under nitrogen and laboratory atmospheres compared with cartilage samples.

When the AC or hydrogel contact is under load, it operates in a biphasic lubrication regime[89]. The interstitial fluid is squeezed from the extracellular matrix into the contact area, and this exudation of the pressurised interstitial fluid helps to achieve low COF values. To sustain this effect over time, the contact bodies need to be adequately rehydrated, meaning that they must remain in a swollen state. In the cartilage-on-cartilage or cartilage-on-hydrogel configurations, rehydration can occur simply because of the migrating contact area[90]. The results of *pHEMA N2* correspond more to the stationary contact area and evoke inadequate rehydration, which aligns with its lowest swelling ratio and low swelling rate in the synovial fluid. Shi et al.[91] reported a doubling of the COF values when the water content of the PVA hydrogel was reduced by approximately 15%. Preparation of pHEMA hydrogels in a laboratory setting and under an inert nitrogen atmosphere also resulted in a different Young's moduli (0.93 ± 0.07 MPa for *pHEMA air* vs 0.82 ± 0.05 MPa for *pHEMA N2*) which could influence COF values. Shi et al.[92] also found lower COF values for PVA/PVP hydrogels as the compressive tangent modulus increased. Furthermore, different environmental conditions during pHEMA hydrogel preparation led to variations in surface morphology (smooth vs. corrugated surface). According to Rudge et al.[93] under a certain level of normal load, surface asperities are flattened, leading to a smoother surface where the COF is determined by the material properties. However, we believe that the deformation

of surface asperities causes a local increase in contact pressure, resulting in greater pressurised fluid exudation from the hydrogel matrix to the contact area. Additionally, surface wrinkles create a larger surface area, from which the pressurised interstitial fluid can be squeezed into the contact area. Therefore, the *pHEMA air* should exhibit better friction.

Permeability coefficient of pHEMA hydrogels

The ability of cartilage to support loads through interstitial fluid pressurisation is dependent on its low hydraulic permeability. Human articular cartilage permeability is influenced by factors such as tissue depth, applied pressure, and water content. In this study, permeability was calculated based on the stress relaxation behaviour following the method outlined by Yamaguchi et al. (2018)[61]. The permeability values of human cartilage typically range from 10^{-15} to 10^{-16} $\text{m}^4 \cdot \text{Ns}^{-1}$ [94–102], with a tendency to decrease with increasing depth and increase under higher pressures [95,103]. These values are consistent with the results presented in **Table 2** for *pHEMA air*. Additionally, *pHEMA N2* exhibited a slightly higher permeability coefficient than that reported for human cartilage.

Table 2. Calculated hydraulic permeability coefficients of *pHEMA N2* and *pHEMA air*.

	Permeability coefficient (m^4/Ns)	SD
<i>pHEMA N2</i>	$2.17 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$2.81 \cdot 10^{-14}$
<i>pHEMA air</i>	$8.79 \cdot 10^{-15}$	$4.82 \cdot 10^{-15}$
<i>Human AC</i>	$1 \cdot 10^{-15} - 10^{-16}$	**[94–102]

The relationship between cartilage permeability and friction is complex and multifaceted. Increased permeability, often associated with cartilage degradation, can lead to reduced interstitial fluid pressurisation, resulting in higher friction coefficients[100,104]. This fluid pressurisation is vital for load support and maintaining low friction in the articular cartilage[105,106]. The depletion of glycosaminoglycans (GAGs), which increase permeability, leads to higher friction owing to a reduction in biphasic lubrication[107]. Conversely, reinforcing cartilage with an interpenetrating polymer network can lower the friction by enhancing the interstitial fluid phase[108]. Additionally, increased leakage at the osteochondral junction, often observed in conditions such as OA, can accelerate fluid de-pressurisation, further elevating friction levels[109]. Hence, in terms of

permeability, *pHEMA air* is a faithful model of healthy human cartilage whereas *pHEMA N2* could be a model of cartilage with incipient osteoarthritis.

CONCLUSION

Our research has demonstrated that a relatively simple and very known polymeric material, such as a poly(hydroxyethyl methacrylate) (pHEMA) hydrogel, can prove to be a suitable alternative to the commonly used poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) hydrogels in tribological measurements. By creating a defined atmosphere, it is possible to prepare a corrugated transparent material similar to the articular cartilage in terms of morphology, tensile strength, and coefficient of friction, thereby demonstrating the potential of pHEMA hydrogels as a suitable tribological model material. Regarding the results of permeability, the pHEMA hydrogels prepared under a laboratory atmosphere may represent a faithful model of healthy human cartilage, whereas pHEMA hydrogels prepared under a nitrogen atmosphere may be a model of cartilage with incipient osteoarthritis expressing similar hydraulic permeability.

The potential of this material for superlubricity can be further enhanced by exploring various lipid compositions and their interactions with the porous structure of the hydrogel. The ability to fine-tune the properties of pHEMA hydrogels through controlled atmospheric preparation opens possibilities for creating customised gradient layered models that mimic specific stages of cartilage health or disease. Furthermore, the superior tribological performance of pHEMA hydrogels compared to PVA could lead to more accurate and reliable results in future studies on joint mechanics and cartilage degeneration.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found online as a Dataset at Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14824950>.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AC	articular cartilage
ANOVA	analysis of variance
ATR-FTIR	attenuated total reflectance fourier transform infrared spectroscopy
CD	cast-drying
COF	coefficient of friction
DC	diffusion coefficient
DMPA	dimethoxy-2-phenylacetophenone
ECM	extracellular matrix
EGDMA	ethylene glycol dimethyl acrylate
FT	freeze-thaw
FTIR	fourier transform infrared spectroscopy
GAGs	glycosaminoglycans
HA	hyaluronic acid
HEMA	2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate
OA	osteoarthritis
PAA	polyacrylic acid
PAM	polyacrylamide
PANa	sodium phytate
PBO	poly(p-phenylene-2,6-benzobisoxazole)
PBS	phosphate buffer
PE	polyethylene glycol
PEG	polyethylene glycol
PGF	phosphate glass fibres
pHEMA	poly(hydroxyethyl methacrylate)
PVA	polyvinyl alcohol
PS	physiological solution
SD	standard deviation
SF	synovial fluid

REFERENCES

- [1] I. Uzieliene, D. Bironaite, E. Bagdonas, J. Pachaleva, A. Sobolev, W.-B. Tsai, G. Kvederas, E. Bernotiene, The Effects of Mechanical Load on Chondrogenic Responses of Bone Marrow Mesenchymal Stem Cells and Chondrocytes Encapsulated in Chondroitin Sulfate-Based Hydrogel, *Int J Mol Sci* 24 (2023) 2915. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24032915>.

- [2] T. Hodgkinson, I.N. Amado, F.J. O'Brien, O.D. Kennedy, The role of mechanobiology in bone and cartilage model systems in characterizing initiation and progression of osteoarthritis, *APL Bioeng* 6 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0068277>.
- [3] C.B. Carballo, Y. Nakagawa, I. Sekiya, S.A. Rodeo, Basic Science of Articular Cartilage, *Clin Sports Med* 36 (2017) 413–425. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csm.2017.02.001>.
- [4] S.J. Gilbert, C.S. Bonnet, E.J. Blain, Mechanical Cues: Bidirectional Reciprocity in the Extracellular Matrix Drives Mechano-Signalling in Articular Cartilage, *Int J Mol Sci* 22 (2021) 13595. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms222413595>.
- [5] D. Heinegård, Fell-Muir Lecture: Proteoglycans and more – from molecules to biology, *Int J Exp Pathol* 90 (2009) 575–586. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2613.2009.00695.x>.
- [6] A.J. Sophia Fox, A. Bedi, S.A. Rodeo, The Basic Science of Articular Cartilage: Structure, Composition, and Function, *Sports Health: A Multidisciplinary Approach* 1 (2009) 461–468. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1941738109350438>.
- [7] X.L. LU, V.C. MOW, Biomechanics of Articular Cartilage and Determination of Material Properties, *Med Sci Sports Exerc* 40 (2008) 193–199. <https://doi.org/10.1249/mss.0b013e31815cb1fc>.
- [8] E. Belluzzi, S. Todros, A. Pozzuoli, P. Ruggieri, E.L. Carniel, A. Berardo, Human Cartilage Biomechanics: Experimental and Theoretical Approaches towards the Identification of Mechanical Properties in Healthy and Osteoarthritic Conditions, *Processes* 11 (2023) 1014. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr11041014>.
- [9] H. Mahmood, D. Eckold, I. Stead, D.E.T. Shepherd, D.M. Espino, K.D. Dearn, A method for the assessment of the coefficient of friction of articular cartilage and a replacement biomaterial, *J Mech Behav Biomed Mater* 103 (2020) 103580. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2019.103580>.
- [10] J.M. Patel, B.C. Wise, E.D. Bonnevie, R.L. Mauck, A Systematic Review and Guide to Mechanical Testing for Articular Cartilage Tissue Engineering, *Tissue Eng Part C Methods* 25 (2019) 593–608. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ten.tec.2019.0116>.
- [11] E. Belluzzi, S. Todros, A. Pozzuoli, P. Ruggieri, E.L. Carniel, A. Berardo, Human Cartilage Biomechanics: Experimental and Theoretical Approaches towards the Identification of Mechanical Properties in Healthy and Osteoarthritic Conditions, *Processes* 11 (2023) 1014. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr11041014>.
- [12] W. Xu, J. Zhu, J. Hu, L. Xiao, Engineering the biomechanical microenvironment of chondrocytes towards articular cartilage tissue engineering, *Life Sci* 309 (2022) 121043. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lfs.2022.121043>.
- [13] N. Petitjean, P. Canadas, P. Royer, D. Noël, S. Le Floc'h, Cartilage biomechanics: From the basic facts to the challenges of tissue engineering, *J Biomed Mater Res A* 111 (2023) 1067–1089. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm.a.37478>.
- [14] C. De Bari, A.J. Roelofs, Stem cell-based therapeutic strategies for cartilage defects and osteoarthritis, *Curr Opin Pharmacol* 40 (2018) 74–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coph.2018.03.009>.

- [15] C. Zhu, W. Zhang, Z. Shao, Z. Wang, B. Chang, X. Ding, Y. Yang, Biodegradable glass fiber reinforced PVA hydrogel for cartilage repair: mechanical properties, ions release behavior and cell recruitment, *Journal of Materials Research and Technology* 23 (2023) 154–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2022.12.166>.
- [16] N. Sakai, S. Yarimitsu, Y. Sawae, M. Komori, T. Murakami, Biomimetic artificial cartilage: fibre-reinforcement of PVA hydrogel to promote biphasic lubrication mechanism, *Biosurf Biotribol* 5 (2019) 13–19. <https://doi.org/10.1049/bsbt.2018.0031>.
- [17] C. Zhu, W. Zhang, Z. Shao, Z. Wang, B. Chang, X. Ding, Y. Yang, Biodegradable glass fiber reinforced PVA hydrogel for cartilage repair: mechanical properties, ions release behavior and cell recruitment, *Journal of Materials Research and Technology* 23 (2023) 154–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2022.12.166>.
- [18] T. Miao, E.J. Miller, C. McKenzie, R.A. Oldinski, Physically crosslinked polyvinyl alcohol and gelatin interpenetrating polymer network theta-gels for cartilage regeneration, *J Mater Chem B* 3 (2015) 9242–9249. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5TB00989H>.
- [19] A.C. Branco, A.S. Oliveira, I. Monteiro, P. Nolasco, D.C. Silva, C.G. Figueiredo-Pina, R. Colaço, A.P. Serro, PVA-Based Hydrogels Loaded with Diclofenac for Cartilage Replacement, *Gels* 8 (2022) 143. <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels8030143>.
- [20] A.S. Oliveira, O. Seidi, N. Ribeiro, R. Colaço, A.P. Serro, Tribomechanical Comparison between PVA Hydrogels Obtained Using Different Processing Conditions and Human Cartilage, *Materials* 12 (2019) 3413. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma12203413>.
- [21] S. SASAKI, S. YARIMITSU, T. MURAKAMI, A. SUZUKI, Effect of Drying on the Frictional Properties of PVA Cast Gel, *KOBUNSHI RONBUNSHU* 72 (2015) 760–764. <https://doi.org/10.1295/koron.2015-0036>.
- [22] M. Kobayashi, H.S. Hyu, Development and Evaluation of Polyvinyl Alcohol-Hydrogels as an Artificial Articular Cartilage for Orthopedic Implants, *Materials* 3 (2010) 2753–2771. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma3042753>.
- [23] T. Pires, A.S. Oliveira, A.C. Marques, M. Salema-Oom, C.G. Figueiredo-Pina, D. Silva, A.P. Serro, Effects of Non-Conventional Sterilisation Methods on PBO-Reinforced PVA Hydrogels for Cartilage Replacement, *Gels* 8 (2022) 640. <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels8100640>.
- [24] Z. Ye, H. Lu, E. Jia, J. Chen, L. Fu, Organic solvents enhance polyvinyl alcohol/polyethylene glycol self-healing hydrogels for artificial cartilage, *Polym Adv Technol* 33 (2022) 3455–3469. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pat.5799>.
- [25] T. Pires, A.S. Oliveira, A.C. Marques, M. Salema-Oom, C.G. Figueiredo-Pina, D. Silva, A.P. Serro, Effects of Non-Conventional Sterilisation Methods on PBO-Reinforced PVA Hydrogels for Cartilage Replacement, *Gels* 8 (2022) 640. <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels8100640>.
- [26] U. Koc, Y. Aykut, R. Eren, Natural fibers woven fabric reinforced hydrogel composites for enhanced mechanical properties, *Journal of Industrial Textiles* 51 (2022) 6315S–6332S. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1528083720944485>.

- [27] U. Koc, Y. Aykut, R. Eren, Regenerated cellulose woven fabric reinforced hydrogel composite, *The Journal of The Textile Institute* 113 (2022) 906–914. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405000.2021.1908007>.
- [28] J.L. Holloway, A.M. Lowman, M.R. VanLandingham, G.R. Palmese, Interfacial optimization of fiber-reinforced hydrogel composites for soft fibrous tissue applications, *Acta Biomater* 10 (2014) 3581–3589. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2014.05.004>.
- [29] J.L. Holloway, A.M. Lowman, M.R. VanLandingham, G.R. Palmese, Chemical grafting for improved interfacial shear strength in UHMWPE/PVA-hydrogel fiber-based composites used as soft fibrous tissue replacements, *Compos Sci Technol* 85 (2013) 118–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2013.06.007>.
- [30] C. Zhu, W. Zhang, Z. Shao, Z. Wang, B. Chang, X. Ding, Y. Yang, Biodegradable glass fiber reinforced PVA hydrogel for cartilage repair: mechanical properties, ions release behavior and cell recruitment, *Journal of Materials Research and Technology* 23 (2023) 154–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2022.12.166>.
- [31] C. Yin, Z. Huang, Y. Zhang, K. Ren, S. Liu, H. Luo, Q. Zhang, Y. Wan, Strong, tough, and elastic poly(vinyl alcohol)/polyacrylamide DN hydrogels based on the Hofmeister effect for articular cartilage replacement, *J Mater Chem B* 12 (2024) 3079–3091. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3TB02637J>.
- [32] A.C. Branco, A.S. Oliveira, I. Monteiro, P. Nolasco, D.C. Silva, C.G. Figueiredo-Pina, R. Colaço, A.P. Serro, PVA-Based Hydrogels Loaded with Diclofenac for Cartilage Replacement, *Gels* 8 (2022) 143. <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels8030143>.
- [33] S. Zhang, Y. Li, H. Zhang, G. Wang, H. Wei, X. Zhang, N. Ma, Bioinspired Conductive Hydrogel with Ultrahigh Toughness and Stable Antiswelling Properties for Articular Cartilage Replacement, *ACS Mater Lett* 3 (2021) 807–814. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmaterialslett.1c00203>.
- [34] E. Drápalová, L. Michlovská, H. Poštulková, I. Chamradová, B. Lipový, J. Holoubek, L. Vacek, F. Růžička, M. Hanslianová, T. Svobodová, E. Černá, B. Hrdličková, L. Vojtová, Antimicrobial Cost-Effective Transparent Hydrogel Films from Renewable Gum Karaya/Chitosan Polysaccharides for Modern Wound Dressings, *ACS Appl Polym Mater* 5 (2023) 2774–2786. https://doi.org/10.1021/ACSAPM.3C00025/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/AP3C00025_0011.JPG.
- [35] L. Vacek, D. Polašník Kleknerová, B. Lipový, J. Holoubek, D. Matysková, E. Černá, J. Brtníková, E. Jeklová, Kobzová, L. Janda, L. Lišková, D. Diabelko, T. Botka, R. Pantůček, F. Růžička, L. Vojtová, Phage therapy combined with Gum Karaya injectable hydrogels for treatment of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* deep wound infection in a porcine model, *Int J Pharm* 660 (2024) 124348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJPHARM.2024.124348>.
- [36] Z. Ye, H. Lu, E. Jia, J. Chen, L. Fu, Organic solvents enhance polyvinyl alcohol/polyethylene glycol self-healing hydrogels for artificial cartilage, *Polym Adv Technol* 33 (2022) 3455–3469. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pat.5799>.

- [37] Z. Ye, H. Lu, G. Chai, C. Wu, J. Chen, L. Lv, Glycerol-modified poly(vinyl alcohol)/poly(ethylene glycol) self-healing hydrogel for artificial cartilage, *Polym Int* 72 (2023) 27–38. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pi.6444>.
- [38] A.S. Oliveira, O. Seidi, N. Ribeiro, R. Colaço, A.P. Serro, Tribomechanical Comparison between PVA Hydrogels Obtained Using Different Processing Conditions and Human Cartilage, *Materials* 12 (2019) 3413. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma12203413>.
- [39] C. Yin, Z. Huang, Y. Zhang, K. Ren, S. Liu, H. Luo, Q. Zhang, Y. Wan, Strong, tough, and elastic poly(vinyl alcohol)/polyacrylamide DN hydrogels based on the Hofmeister effect for articular cartilage replacement, *J Mater Chem B* 12 (2024) 3079–3091. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3TB02637J>.
- [40] Y. Chen, J. Song, S. Wang, W. Liu, PVA-Based Hydrogels: Promising Candidates for Articular Cartilage Repair, *Macromol Biosci* 21 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1002/mabi.202100147>.
- [41] M. Ranuša, M. Ondra, D. Rebenda, M. Vrbka, J. Gallo, I. Křupka, Effects of Viscosupplementation on Tribological Behaviour of Articular Cartilage, *Lubricants* 10 (2022) 361. <https://doi.org/10.3390/lubricants10120361>.
- [42] H. Mahmood, D. Eckold, I. Stead, D.E.T. Shepherd, D.M. Espino, K.D. Dearn, A method for the assessment of the coefficient of friction of articular cartilage and a replacement biomaterial, *J Mech Behav Biomed Mater* 103 (2020) 103580. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2019.103580>.
- [43] S.A.H. de Vries, M. van Doeselaar, H.J. Kaper, P.K. Sharma, K. Ito, Notochordal cell matrix as a bioactive lubricant for the osteoarthritic joint, *Sci Rep* 8 (2018) 8875. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-27130-9>.
- [44] F. Li, A. Wang, C. Wang, Analysis of friction between articular cartilage and polyvinyl alcohol hydrogel artificial cartilage, *J Mater Sci Mater Med* 27 (2016) 87. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10856-016-5700-y>.
- [45] P. Čípek, M. Vrbka, D. Rebenda, D. Nečas, I. Křupka, Biotribology of Synovial Cartilage: A New Method for Visualization of Lubricating Film and Simultaneous Measurement of the Friction Coefficient, *Materials* 13 (2020) 2075. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13092075>.
- [46] J. Seror, L. Zhu, R. Goldberg, A.J. Day, J. Klein, Supramolecular synergy in the boundary lubrication of synovial joints, *Nat Commun* 6 (2015) 6497. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms7497>.
- [47] R. Krishnan, M. Kopacz, G.A. Ateshian, Experimental verification of the role of interstitial fluid pressurization in cartilage lubrication, *Journal of Orthopaedic Research* 22 (2004) 565–570. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orthres.2003.07.002>.
- [48] Z. Hua, M. Hu, Y. Chen, X. Huang, L. Gao, Investigation of the Friction Properties of a New Artificial Imitation Cartilage Material: PHEMA/Glycerol Gel, *Materials* 16 (2023) 4023. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma16114023>.
- [49] M.F. Passos, N.M.S. Carvalho, A.A. Rodrigues, V.P. Bavaresco, A.L. Jardini, M.R.W. Maciel, R. Maciel Filho, PHEMA Hydrogels Obtained by Infrared Radiation for Cartilage

- Tissue Engineering, International Journal of Chemical Engineering 2019 (2019) 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/4249581>.
- [50] T. Pires, A.S. Oliveira, A.C. Marques, M. Salema-Oom, C.G. Figueiredo-Pina, D. Silva, A.P. Serro, Effects of Non-Conventional Sterilisation Methods on PBO-Reinforced PVA Hydrogels for Cartilage Replacement, *Gels* 8 (2022) 640. <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels8100640>.
- [51] E.B. Makarova, M.A. Korch, F.A. Fadeyev, D.G. Bliznets, A. V. Bugayova, T.F. Shklyar, A.P. Safronov, K.A. Nokhrin, F.A. Blyakhman, Testing of the pHEMA hydrogel as an implantation material for replacement of osteochondral defects in animals, *Russian Journal of Transplantology and Artificial Organs* 24 (2022) 71–82. <https://doi.org/10.15825/1995-1191-2022-2-71-82>.
- [52] R. Hobzova, J. Hrib, J. Sirc, E. Karpushkin, J. Michalek, O. Janouskova, P. Gatenholm, Embedding of Bacterial Cellulose Nanofibers within PHEMA Hydrogel Matrices: Tunable Stiffness Composites with Potential for Biomedical Applications, *J Nanomater* 2018 (2018) 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/5217095>.
- [53] M. Zare, A. Bigam, M. Zare, H. Luo, E. Rezvani Ghomi, S. Ramakrishna, pHEMA: An Overview for Biomedical Applications, *Int J Mol Sci* 22 (2021) 6376. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22126376>.
- [54] T. Krajňák, E. Černá, M. Šuráňová, T. Šamořil, D. Zicha, L. Vojtová, J. Čechal, Replica-mold nanopatterned PHEMA hydrogel surfaces for ophthalmic applications, *Sci Rep* 12 (2022) 14497. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-18564-3>.
- [55] P. Hilšer, A. Suchánková, K. Mendová, K.E. Filipič, M. Daniel, M. Vrbka, A new insight into more effective viscosupplementation based on the synergy of hyaluronic acid and phospholipids for cartilage friction reduction, *Biotribology* 25 (2021) 100166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotri.2021.100166>.
- [56] E. Karadag, D. Saraydin, N. Sahiner, O. Güven, RADIATION INDUCED ACRYLAMIDE/CITRIC ACID HYDROGELS AND THEIR SWELLING BEHAVIORS, *Journal of Macromolecular Science, Part A* 38 (2001) 1105–1121. <https://doi.org/10.1081/MA-100107132>.
- [57] E. Manaila, G. Craciun, D. Ighigeanu, C. Cimpeanu, C. Barna, V. Fugaru, Hydrogels Synthesized by Electron Beam Irradiation for Heavy Metal Adsorption, *Materials* 10 (2017) 540. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma10050540>.
- [58] D. Rebenda, M. Vrbka, P. Čípek, E. Toropitsyn, D. Nečas, M. Pravda, M. Hartl, On the Dependence of Rheology of Hyaluronic Acid Solutions and Frictional Behavior of Articular Cartilage, *Materials* 13 (2020) 2659. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13112659>.
- [59] D. Rebenda, M. Vrbka, D. Nečas, E. Toropitsyn, S. Yarimitsu, P. Čípek, M. Pravda, M. Hartl, Rheological and frictional analysis of viscosupplements towards improved lubrication of human joints, *Tribol Int* 160 (2021) 107030. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2021.107030>.
- [60] A. Galandáková, J. Ulrichová, K. Langová, A. Hanáková, M. Vrbka, M. Hartl, J. Gallo, Characteristics of synovial fluid required for optimization of lubrication fluid for

- biotribological experiments, *J Biomed Mater Res B Appl Biomater* 105 (2017) 1422–1431. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm.b.33663>.
- [61] T. Yamaguchi, R. Sato, Y. Sawae, Propagation of Fatigue Cracks in Friction of Brittle Hydrogels, *Gels* 4 (2018) 53. <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels4020053>.
- [62] Y. Liu, P. Wang, J. Wang, B. Xu, J. Xu, J. Yuan, Y. Yu, Q. Wang, Transparent and tough poly(2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate) hydrogels prepared in water/IL mixtures, *New Journal of Chemistry* 44 (2020) 4092–4098. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0NJ00214C>.
- [63] A. Podestà, E. Ranucci, L. Macchi, G. Bongiorno, P. Ferruti, P. Milani, Micro- and Nanoscale Modification of Poly(2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate) Hydrogels by AFM Lithography and Nanoparticle Incorporation, *J Nanosci Nanotechnol* 5 (2005) 425–430. <https://doi.org/10.1166/jnn.2005.061>.
- [64] Y. Yun, Y. Guan, Y. Zhang, Patterned PHEMA Films Synthesized by Redox Polymerization for Multicellular Spheroid Generation, *Ind Eng Chem Res* 58 (2019) 10713–10723. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.9b01517>.
- [65] H. Kaczmarek, P. Gałka, J. Kowalonek, Influence of a photoinitiator on the photochemical stability of poly(methyl methacrylate) studied with fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, *J Appl Polym Sci* 115 (2010) 1598–1607. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.31166>.
- [66] E. Oyarce, G.D.C. Pizarro, D.P. Oyarzún, C. Zúñiga, J. Sánchez, HYDROGELS BASED ON 2-HYDROXYETHYL METHACRYLATE: SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND HYDRATION CAPACITY, *Journal of the Chilean Chemical Society* 65 (2020) 4682–4685. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0717-97072020000104682>.
- [67] E. Vargün, A. Usanmaz, Degradation of Poly(2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate) Obtained by Radiation in Aqueous Solution, *Journal of Macromolecular Science, Part A* 47 (2010) 882–891. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10601325.2010.501304>.
- [68] S. Kim, B.H. Shin, C. Yang, S. Jeong, J.H. Shim, M.H. Park, Y. Bin Choy, C.Y. Heo, K. Lee, Development of Poly(HEMA-Am) Polymer Hydrogel Filler for Soft Tissue Reconstruction by Facile Polymerization, *Polymers (Basel)* 10 (2018) 772. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym10070772>.
- [69] X. Yang, M. Cui, J. Zhou, L. Zhang, H. Zhou, Z. Luo, L. Zhou, H. Hu, Surface Fluorination Modification and Anti-Biofouling Study of a pHEMA Hydrogel, *ACS Appl Bio Mater* 4 (2021) 523–532. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsabm.0c01071>.
- [70] V. Mucci, C. Vallo, Efficiency of 2,2-dimethoxy-2-phenylacetophenone for the photopolymerization of methacrylate monomers in thick sections, *J Appl Polym Sci* 123 (2012) 418–425. <https://doi.org/10.1002/APP.34473>.
- [71] N. Kanagathara, K. Senthilkumar, V. Sabari, V. Ragavendran, S. Elangovan, Structural and Vibrational Investigation of Benzil-(1,2-Diphenylethane-1,2-Dione): Experimental and Theoretical Studies, *J Chem* 2022 (2022) 5968496. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/5968496>.
- [72] S.M. Alqahtani, R.S. Al Khulaifi, M. Alassaf, W.S. Saeed, I. Bedja, A. Aldarwesh, A. Aljubailah, A. Semlali, T. Aouak, Preparation and Characterization of Poly(vinyl Acetate-co-2-hydroxyethyl Methacrylate) and In Vitro Application as Contact Lens for Acyclovir Delivery, *Int J Mol Sci* 24 (2023) 5483. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24065483>.

- [73] J. Zhu, J. Wang, Q. Liu, Y. Liu, L. Wang, C. He, H. Wang, Anisotropic tough poly(2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate) hydrogels fabricated by directional freezing redox polymerization, *J. Mater. Chem. B* 1 (2013) 978–986. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C2TB00288D>.
- [74] R.K. Bose, K.K.S. Lau, Mechanical Properties of Ultrahigh Molecular Weight PHEMA Hydrogels Synthesized Using Initiated Chemical Vapor Deposition, *Biomacromolecules* 11 (2010) 2116–2122. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bm100498a>.
- [75] E.M. Boazak, V.K. Greene, D.T. Auguste, The effect of heterobifunctional crosslinkers on HEMA hydrogel modulus and toughness, *PLoS One* 14 (2019) e0215895. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0215895>.
- [76] M.N. Moghadam, D.P. Pioletti, Improving hydrogels' toughness by increasing the dissipative properties of their network, *J Mech Behav Biomed Mater* 41 (2015) 161–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2014.10.010>.
- [77] N. Petitjean, P. Canadas, P. Royer, D. Noël, S. Le Floch, Cartilage biomechanics: From the basic facts to the challenges of tissue engineering, *J Biomed Mater Res A* 111 (2023) 1067–1089. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm.a.37478>.
- [78] S. Akizuki, V.C. Mow, F. Müller, J.C. Pita, D.S. Howell, D.H. Manicourt, Tensile properties of human knee joint cartilage: I. Influence of ionic conditions, weight bearing, and fibrillation on the tensile modulus, *Journal of Orthopaedic Research* 4 (1986) 379–392. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jor.1100040401>.
- [79] T. Murakami, K. Nakashima, Y. Sawae, N. Sakai, N. Hosoda, Roles of adsorbed film and gel layer in hydration lubrication for articular cartilage, *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part J: Journal of Engineering Tribology* 223 (2009) 287–295. <https://doi.org/10.1243/13506501JET536>.
- [80] S.E. Majd, R. Kuijer, A. Köwitsch, T. Groth, T.A. Schmidt, P.K. Sharma, Both hyaluronan and collagen type II keep proteoglycan 4 (lubricin) at the cartilage surface in a condition that provides low friction during boundary lubrication, *Langmuir* 30 (2014) 14566–14572. https://doi.org/10.1021/LA504345C/SUPPL_FILE/LA504345C_SI_001.PDF.
- [81] S. Voinier, A.C. Moore, J.M. Benson, C. Price, D.L. Burris, The Modes and Competing Rates of Cartilage Fluid Loss and Recovery, *SSRN Electronic Journal* (2021). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3831566>.
- [82] E.G. Baylon, M.E. Levenston, Osmotic Swelling Responses Are Conserved Across Cartilaginous Tissues With Varied Sulfated-Glycosaminoglycan Contents, *Journal of Orthopaedic Research* 38 (2020) 785–792. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jor.24521>.
- [83] A.C. Moore, D.L. Burris, Tribological rehydration of cartilage and its potential role in preserving joint health, *Osteoarthritis Cartilage* 25 (2017) 99–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joca.2016.09.018>.
- [84] H. Ayhan, F. Ayhan, Water based PHEMA hydrogels for controlled drug delivery, *Turkish Journal of Biochemistry* 43 (2018) 228–239. <https://doi.org/10.1515/tjb-2017-0250>.

- [85] J.P. Baker, H.W. Blanch, J.M. Prausnitz, Swelling properties of acrylamide-based ampholytic hydrogels: comparison of experiment with theory, *Polymer (Guildf)* 36 (1995) 1061–1069. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-3861\(95\)93608-O](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-3861(95)93608-O).
- [86] S. Pan, M. Xia, H. Li, X. Jiang, P. He, Z. Sun, Y. Zhang, Transparent, high-strength, stretchable, sensitive and anti-freezing poly(vinyl alcohol) ionic hydrogel strain sensors for human motion monitoring, *J Mater Chem C Mater* 8 (2020) 2827–2837. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9TC06338B>.
- [87] M.F. Refojo, Hydrophobic interaction in poly(2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate) homogeneous hydrogel, *J Polym Sci A1* 5 (1967) 3103–3113. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pol.1967.150051211>.
- [88] S.J. Kim, S.R. Shin, S.M. Lee, I.Y. Kim, S.I. Kim, Electromechanical properties of hydrogels based on chitosan and poly(hydroxyethyl methacrylate) in NaCl solution, *Smart Mater Struct* 13 (2004) 1036–1039. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0964-1726/13/5/008>.
- [89] S. Park, C.T. Hung, G.A. Ateshian, Mechanical response of bovine articular cartilage under dynamic unconfined compression loading at physiological stress levels, *Osteoarthritis Cartilage* 12 (2004) 65–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joca.2003.08.005>.
- [90] M. Caligaris, G.A. Ateshian, Effects of sustained interstitial fluid pressurization under migrating contact area, and boundary lubrication by synovial fluid, on cartilage friction, *Osteoarthritis Cartilage* 16 (2008) 1220–1227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joca.2008.02.020>.
- [91] Y. Shi, D. Xiong, Y. Liu, N. Wang, X. Zhao, Swelling, mechanical and friction properties of PVA/PVP hydrogels after swelling in osmotic pressure solution, *Materials Science and Engineering: C* 65 (2016) 172–180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2016.04.042>.
- [92] Y. Shi, D.S. Xiong, Y. Peng, N. Wang, Effects of polymerization degree on recovery behavior of PVA/PVP hydrogels as potential articular cartilage prosthesis after fatigue test, *Express Polym Lett* 10 (2016) 125–138. <https://doi.org/10.3144/expresspolymlett.2016.13>.
- [93] R.E.D. Rudge, E. Scholten, J.A. Dijksman, Natural and induced surface roughness determine frictional regimes in hydrogel pairs, *Tribol Int* 141 (2020) 105903. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2019.105903>.
- [94] W.Y. Gu, H. Yao, C.Y. Huang, H.S. Cheung, New insight into deformation-dependent hydraulic permeability of gels and cartilage, and dynamic behavior of agarose gels in confined compression, *J Biomech* 36 (2003) 593–598. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9290\(02\)00437-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9290(02)00437-2).
- [95] J.S. Jurvelin, M.D. Buschmann, E.B. Hunziker, Mechanical anisotropy of the human knee articular cartilage in compression, *Proc Inst Mech Eng H* 217 (2003) 215–219. <https://doi.org/10.1243/095441103765212712>.
- [96] R.K. Korhonen, M.S. Laasanen, J. Töyräs, J. Rieppo, J. Hirvonen, H.J. Helminen, J.S. Jurvelin, Comparison of the equilibrium response of articular cartilage in unconfined compression, confined compression and indentation, *J Biomech* 35 (2002) 903–909. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9290\(02\)00052-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9290(02)00052-0).

- [97] J. Mansour, V. Mow, The permeability of articular cartilage under compressive strain and at high pressures, *J Bone Joint Surg* 58 (1976) 509–516. <https://doi.org/10.2106/00004623-197658040-00014>.
- [98] V.C. Mow, S.C. Kuei, W.M. Lai, C.G. Armstrong, Biphasic Creep and Stress Relaxation of Articular Cartilage in Compression: Theory and Experiments, *J Biomech Eng* 102 (1980) 73–84. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.3138202>.
- [99] B. Reynaud, T.M. Quinn, Anisotropic hydraulic permeability in compressed articular cartilage, *J Biomech* 39 (2006) 131–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2004.10.015>.
- [100] M.A. Soltz, G.A. Ateshian, Interstitial Fluid Pressurization During Confined Compression Cyclical Loading of Articular Cartilage, *Ann Biomed Eng* 28 (2000) 150–159. <https://doi.org/10.1114/1.239>.
- [101] Y. Wu, S.E. Cisewski, B.L. Sachs, J.V.D. Pellegrini, M.J. Kern, E.H. Slate, H. Yao, The region-dependent biomechanical and biochemical properties of bovine cartilaginous endplate, *J Biomech* 48 (2015) 3185–3191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2015.07.005>.
- [102] T.-Y. Yuan, C.-Y. Huang, W. Yong Gu, Novel Technique for Online Characterization of Cartilaginous Tissue Properties, *J Biomech Eng* 133 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4004920>.
- [103] F. Boschetti, C. Miotti, F. Massi, M. Colombo, V. Quaglioni, G.M. Peretti, R. Pietrabissa, An experimental study on human articular cartilage permeability, in: *Proceedings of the Second Joint 24th Annual Conference and the Annual Fall Meeting of the Biomedical Engineering Society* [Engineering in Medicine and Biology, IEEE, 2002: pp. 2581–2582 vol.3. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IEMBS.2002.1053436>.
- [104] G.A. Ateshian, The role of interstitial fluid pressurization in articular cartilage lubrication, *J Biomech* 42 (2009) 1163–1176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2009.04.040>.
- [105] G.A. Ateshian, H. Wang, W.M. Lai, The Role of Interstitial Fluid Pressurization and Surface Porosities on the Boundary Friction of Articular Cartilage, *J Tribol* 120 (1998) 241–248. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2834416>.
- [106] A. Stankiewicz, G.A. Ateshian, L.U. Bigliani, V.C. Mow, Permeability of Human Glenohumeral Joint Cartilage, in: *Advances in Bioengineering*, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 1999: pp. 231–232. <https://doi.org/10.1115/IMECE1999-0462>.
- [107] J. Katta, S.S. Pawaskar, Z.M. Jin, E. Ingham, J. Fisher, Effect of load variation on the friction properties of articular cartilage, *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part J: Journal of Engineering Tribology* 221 (2007) 175–181. <https://doi.org/10.1243/13506501JET240>.
- [108] B.G. Cooper, T.B. Lawson, B.D. Snyder, M.W. Grinstaff, Reinforcement of articular cartilage with a tissue-interpenetrating polymer network reduces friction and modulates interstitial fluid load support, *Osteoarthritis Cartilage* 25 (2017) 1143–1149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joca.2017.03.001>.

- [109] Q. Li, S. Miramini, D.W. Smith, B.S. Gardiner, L. Zhang, Osteochondral junction leakage and cartilage joint lubrication, *Comput Methods Programs Biomed* 230 (2023) 107353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmpb.2023.107353>.

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